

General protocol for preparation, purification and characterization of tau oligomers

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Introduction

During amyloid aggregation, monomeric amyloid proteins associate to form dimers, trimers, high-n oligomers, protofibrils and finally fibrils that are deposited in protein plaques (intracellular tau tangles, extracellular A β plaques and presynaptic α -synuclein aggregates). Opposite to mature fibrils, oligomers are comparatively smaller (a few nm), mostly globular and characterized by an antiparallel- β sheet structure rather than parallel cross- β strands found in amyloid fibrils. Therefore, oligomers are not sufficiently distinguishable by thioflavin T (ThT) assay. The inter-ring rotation of the ThT molecule is slowed down when bound to amyloid filament, which is increasing fluorescent yields by factors ranging from 160. Therefore, ThT has become one of the most widely used “gold standards” for selectively identifying and analyzing the formation of amyloid fibrils both in vivo and in vitro and the ThT assay is widely used for monitoring of the kinetics of amyloid self-assembly. Oligomers tend to retain more flexibility in their structure, representing the metastable states among the energy landscape, while fibrils correspond to the ground states of amyloid proteins. On the contrary to fibrillar oligomers, the so-called off-pathway oligomers were shown to inhibit the amyloid fibrilization by depleting the pool of monomers available for fibril nucleation and elongation. However, the role of on- and off-pathway oligomers in the etiology of protein misfolding disease remains controversial. Amyloid fibrillation involves both primary and secondary nucleation. While primary nucleation ensures variability within the oligomers collectively referred to as pre-nucleation clusters, secondary nucleation produces distinct types of filaments. Amyloid oligomers evolve in distinct arrangements producing annular protofibrils, doughnut-shaped structures, curvilinear protofibrils, spherical oligomers or linear-protofibrils with beads-on-a-string morphology observed by cryo-EM, TEM and AFM [1].

Materials:

Sample of full length or truncated tau protein
2 mM thioflavin T (ThT) stock solution
Antibody T22 (Sigma, ABN454)
Antibody DC25 (Institute of Neuroimmunology) or other pan tau antibody
Size exclusion chromatography column Superdex S200 10/30
FPLC system (ACTA Avant)
Desktop thermal shaker
Fluostar omega (BMG Labtech)
Dithiothreitol (DTT)
iBright (Thermo Fisher Scientific)

Procedure:

1. Purify tau proteins to obtain monomeric samples.
2. Prepare tau protein solution in 100 μ M concentration in PBS or 10 mM phosphate buffer.
3. Add DTT to final 10 μ M concentration.

- For analysis with ion mobility MS, prepare tau solution in Ammonium bicarbonate without DTT.
 - Use isotopically ^{13}C , ^{15}N labeled tau proteins for subsequent analysis with solid state and solution state NMR.
4. Monitor aggregation behavior to determine the exponential aggregation phase with the highest oligomer concentration by the continuous measurement of ThT fluorescence using Fluostar omega instrument in black 96 (or 384) well microplates. Use triplicates with 100 μL volume (40 μL for 384 plates).

Figure 1 The kinetics of fibril and oligomer formation Adapted from [1]

5. Perform shaken aggregation reaction (in microplate or Eppendorf tube) and withdraw volume for oligomer isolation at the specific time point determined in step 3.
6. Centrifuge the mixture at 21000 g to get present fibrils
7. Apply the supernatant to the size exclusion column Superdex S200 10/30.
8. Collect the high molecular tau peak.
9. Concentrate the oligomer fraction.
10. Perform the dot blot analysis of the oligomeric fraction. Use primary antibody DC25 (control pan tau antibody) and oligomer specific antibodies T22 and TOMA-1.
11. Use species specific HRP conjugated secondary antibody. Anti-rabbit for T22, anti-mouse for DC25 and TOMA-1.
12. Perform the chemiluminescent detection of signal from dot blot (iBright).
13. Characterize the obtained oligomeric preparation with SDS Page, DLS (SpectroLight 610 or Wyatt DynaPro Nanostar), atomic force microscopy, etc.

Notes:

The onset of the oligomer formation at quiescent conditions can be monitored in small volume (0:8 μL) drops under oil using in situ DLS measurements using SpectroLight 610 instrument (Xstall Concepts).

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References

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